

Performance and stability of premium quality rice varieties in multi-environment trials using AMMI and GGE biplot during the Boro season in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the performance and stability of two advanced rice genotypes, BR9930-2-3-2-2 (V1) and BR9930-2-3-3-1 (V2), compared to three standard varieties- BRRI dhan50 (V3), BRRI dhan63 (V4), and BRRI dhan81 (V5)-across ten agro-ecological zones during the 2021-22 Boro season in Bangladesh. A randomized complete block design (RCBD) was employed with three replications per site to evaluate grain yield, agronomic traits, and genotype-environment interactions (GEI) using AMMI and GGE biplot models. The study revealed significant GEI effects on grain yield, highlighting environmental variability and genotype-specific adaptability. V1 achieved the highest mean yield (6.57 t/ha) with superior performance in several environments, while V2 displayed consistent stability across diverse agro-ecological zones with a mean yield of 6.49 t/ha. The GGE biplot identified V1 as suitable for targeted environments and V2 as the most stable genotype, making it ideal for broader cultivation. These findings underscore the potential of the advanced genotypes for sustainable rice production, particularly in meeting the demand for high-yielding, premium-quality rice in Bangladesh. Further multilocation trials are recommended to validate the stability and adaptability of these genotypes for potential variety release.

INTRODUCTION

About 135 million Bangladeshis rely on rice as their primary food source. It accounts for over 48% of rural employment, approximately two-thirds of total calorie supply, and roughly one-half of an average person's total protein consumption (BRKB, 2024). Over three-quarters of the country's total cultivated land is dedicated to rice, which provides more than 83% of the nation's cereal supply (Government of Bangladesh, 2021). Food security in Bangladesh is the same as rice security (Kabir et al., 2021). The Bangladesh government figured out that rice production peaked at 10.59 million tons in 1971 and reached 37.4 million tons by 2020 (Hassan, 2021). Presently, rice production in Bangladesh grew about 2.5 percent during fiscal year 2023 (Parvez, 2023). Bangladesh achieved food

sufficiency during this time. Although rice breeders mainly focus on yield improvement due to the rapidly growing population, the demand for premium quality grain by rice markets has also consistently increased in recent decades with the improvement in living standards (Alamet al., 2024). Thus, breeding for rice varieties with high yields combined with quality grain is a current need. Therefore, The Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) and government initiatives are now focusing on enhancing rice grain quality and nutrients. To alleviate local and global hunger, efforts have been made to create high-yielding rice varieties of enhanced quality. In response to rising population demands, food security, urbanization, climate change, and shifting dietary preferences, BRRI has introduced 115 high-yielding rice varieties to date, grown in three seasons: Aus,

Aman, and Boro (Bangladesh Rice Knowledge Bank, n.d.). Aman is the main monsoon season (July to November), while Aus follows the dry Boro season (November-December to April-May). Recently, BRRI's plant breeding division developed two advanced lines, pedigree named as BR9930-2-3-2-2) and BR9930-2-3-3-1, for the Boro season, having long slender properties of the grain, However, the performance of yield and stability across sites remains unknown.

Multilocation yield trials (MLYTs) are commonly used to evaluate the yield performance of rice germplasm across several settings. In MLYTs, genotype-environment interaction (GEI) is a major source of variation, which may be attributed to both genetic and non-genetic variables (Ahmed et al., 2024). Variations in yield due to biotic and abiotic stresses, soil fertility, and rainfall create significant differences in genotype performance (Kaya et al., 2006). GEI describes the varied responses of genotypes to different environments, complicating the relationship between phenotypic and genotypic values. By selecting location-specific superior genotypes or choosing broadly adapted, stable ones, GEI effects can be managed (Lakew et al., 2017).

Statistical tools, including joint regression, stability models, AMMI, genotype main effects, and GGE biplots, were used to evaluate genotype stability and adaptability across different environments (Enyew et al., 2021). AMMI and GGE biplots are widely used multivariate models for analyzing genotype stability, adaptation, and ranking, as well as identifying appropriate mega environments (Gauch and Zobel, 1996, Yan and Kang, 2002). AMMI combines genotype and environmental effects with principal component analysis (PCA) of GEI (Sharifi et al., 2017a), while GGE biplots help identify genotypes with high yield and stability in various environments. GGE biplots enable deeper analyses of genotypes and environments, such as determining the best genotype for each environment or identifying stable genotypes across environments (Donoso-Nanculao et al., 2016).

The present study was conducted to evaluate the performance and stability of BRRI-developed breeding lines and recommend suitable lines for

farmers across different environments. We assessed two premium quality rice genotypes and compared them with three released varieties, BRRI dhan50, BRRI dhan63 and BRRI dhan81, across ten agro-ecological zones in Bangladesh to evaluate their yield potential and stability. These findings might be helpful for both breeders and farmers to choose appropriate genotypes for sustainable rice production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

The study evaluated two advanced breeding lines, BR9930-2-3-2-2 (V1) and BR9930-2-3-3-1 (V2), developed by the Plant Breeding Division of the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI). These lines were tested for their grain quality and yield performance in comparison to three widely grown check varieties: BRRI dhan50 (V3), BRRI dhan63 (V4), and BRRI dhan81 (V5). The advanced lines were specifically bred for their premium grain quality, while the check varieties served as benchmarks for yield and stability under local agro-ecological conditions.

Site selection and environmental conditions

The trials were conducted during the 2021–2022 Boro season across ten agro-ecological zones in Bangladesh, capturing a range of climatic and soil conditions. The selected locations were: Sadar, Rangpur (E1); Mithapukur, Rangpur (E2); Paba, Rajshahi (E3); Godagari, Rajshahi (E4); Sadar, Sirajganj (E5); Debidwar, Cumilla (E6); Sadar, Feni (E7); Sadar, Kushtia (E8); Sadar, Habiganj (E9); and BRRI Headquarters, Gazipur (E10). These sites were chosen to evaluate genotype-environment interactions (GEI) and assess the performance and adaptability of the rice genotypes across diverse agro-climatic conditions.

Experimental design

The experiments followed a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications per location. Each experimental plot measured 20 square meters (5 m × 4 m). Seedlings aged 30 to 35 days were transplanted with a spacing of 20 cm

between plants and 15 cm between rows. Seeding was conducted in mid-November 2021, with transplanting dates varying slightly across locations due to local conditions. This design ensured a robust assessment of genotype performance under varied environmental influences.

Crop management practices

Standard crop management practices were uniformly applied across all locations. Fertilizers were used at recommended rates, including urea (270 kg/bigha), triple superphosphate (112 kg/bigha), muriate of potash (150 kg/bigha), gypsum (112 kg/bigha), and zinc sulfate (11 kg/bigha). Urea was applied in three equal splits at 15, 30, and 40 days after transplanting. Irrigation was provided as needed to maintain optimal growth conditions. While insect pests were controlled through appropriate measures, no disease control was implemented to allow the natural assessment of genotype susceptibility and tolerance.

Data collection

Data were collected on both agronomic traits and grain yield. Agronomic traits included plant height (cm), effective tillers per hill, days to 100% flowering, growth duration (days), total grains per panicle, filled grains per panicle, unfilled grains per panicle, and thousand-grain weight (g). Grain yield (t/ha) was recorded from a 9 m² harvested sample area per plot and adjusted to 14% moisture content. These parameters were chosen to provide a comprehensive evaluation of genotype performance and adaptability.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using R software, employing the "metan" package for advanced genotype-environment interaction studies in the R statistical software environment (Team, 2020). Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

was conducted to assess the effects of genotype (G), environment (E), and their interactions (GEI). The AMMI model was used to partition GEI into principal component axes, while GGE biplot analysis provided visual insights into genotype performance, stability, and adaptability. Mean separation was conducted using the least significant difference (LSD) test, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. These statistical tools ensured a detailed understanding of the performance and stability of the tested genotypes across diverse environments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of variance

The combined analysis of variance (ANOVA) across ten environments during the 2021-22 Boro growing season provides valuable insights into the performance of five Premium Quality Rice genotypes. The significant variation observed for replication (R), genotypes (G), environments (E), and genotype-environment interactions (GEI) for almost all the traits and highlights the influence of genetic, environmental, and interaction effects on these traits. The significant p-values ($p \leq 0.001$) for maximum sources of variation confirm the robustness of the ANOVA results (Table 1), indicating that these factors have a substantial impact on the performance of the genotypes.

AMMI analysis of variance

The AMMI ANOVA, highlighting the contributions of different sources of variation to the total sum of squares (TSS) observed in the Premium Quality Rice genotypes dataset for GY. The analysis of variance revealed that GY was significantly affected by E, G and GEI, with a p-value less than 0.001. The majority of the total sum of squares (TSS) in the model was attributed to E (58.21), followed by GEI (27.33). The interaction of the first two principal components (PCs) accounted for approximately 83.2% of the variance at ≤ 0.001 probability (Table 2).

Table 1: Combine ANOVA of yield and its contributing traits on the basis of mean sum of squares of Premium quality rice genotypes during the Boro 2021-22 season

Source of variation	df	Mean sum of squares						
		GY	GD	PHT	TGW	PPM	GPP	UFG
R	2	0.016	0.42	29	0.11	28.7	0.2	8
G	4	5.807***	298.15***	5234***	116.92***	2857.6***	1100.5***	536.2***
E	9	6.46***	120.80***	404***	4.12***	1846.1***	650.1***	552.5***
GEI	36	0.759***	20.08***	38***	1.56***	678.8***	145.3***	189.2***
Error	98	0.130	0.35	8	0.32	67.3	21.9	29.9
Total	149							

^R replication, ^G genotype, ^E environment/ locations, ^{GEI} genotype-environment interaction, *** significant at 0.1% level of probability, ** significant at 0.5 % level of probability, * significant at 1 % level of probability, ns non-significant, ^{df} degrees of freedom, ^{GY} grain yield, ^{GD} growth duration, ^{PHT} plant height, ^{TGW} thousand grain weight, ^{PPM} panicle per m², ^{GPP} grains per panicle, ^{UFG} unfilled grain

Table 2: AMMI analysis of variance of rice grain yield (GY) (t/ha) for four rice genotypes studied under 10 locations during 2022Boro season

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)	Proportion	Accumulated
ENV	9	58.21176	6.467973	61.79605	1.24E-12		
REP(ENV)	20	2.093329	0.104666	0.787764	0.720228		
GEN	4	23.22799	5.806998	43.70595	2.13E-19		
GEN:ENV	36	27.33955	0.759432	5.715809	4.77E-11		
PC1	12	15.06067	1.25506	9.45	0	55.1	55.1
PC2	10	7.69946	0.76995	5.79	0	28.2	83.2
PC3	8	3.21048	0.40131	3.02	0.0051	11.7	95
PC4	6	1.36894	0.22816	1.72	0.127	5	100
Residuals	80	10.62921	0.132865				
Total	185	148.8414	0.804548				

Mean performance of all agronomic traits for Genotype-Environment Interaction

The interaction between genotypes and environments significantly influenced grain yield (GY), growth duration (GD), plant height (PHT), and other yield components (Tables 2). Among the tested genotypes, BR9930-2-3-2-2 genotypes gave statistically higher mean grain yield (6.57 t ha⁻¹) than the other check varieties. Another tested entry BR9930-2-3-3-1 gave statistically similar mean grain yield (6.49 t ha⁻¹) with the check variety BRRi dhan63 (6.31 t ha⁻¹) but higher than the BRRi dhan50 (5.93 t ha⁻¹) and BRRi dhan81 (5.52 t ha⁻¹) but similar yield to that of BR9930-2-3-2-2 (6.57 t ha⁻¹) (table 3).

Mean growth duration over the locations of both the advanced lines BR9930-2-3-2-2 and BR9930-2-3-3-1 were 153 days which was lower than the check variety BRRi dhan50 (157 days) but little bit higher than the check variety BRRi dhan81 and BRRi dhan63 (Table 3). The tallest plant height was 117 cm found in the advanced line BR9930-2-3-3-1 followed by advanced line BR9930-2-3-2-2 (116 cm) (Table 3). However, the mean shortest plant height was found in the check variety BRRi dhan63 (89 cm). Mean plant height of the three check varieties ranged from 89 to 99 cm (Table 3). Thousand grain weight, Panicle production per square meter, grains per panicle and sterility percentage were significantly affected by the interaction of genotypes and environments (Table

3). Lowest thousand grain weight was given by BRR1 dhan50 (18.48g) and the highest was obtained from BR9930-2-3-2-2 genotype (23.62g). The lowest mean number of panicles (248) was produced by the check variety BRR1 dhan81 and the highest number of panicles (272) was produced

by the check variety BRR1 dhan50 (Table 3). The highest grains per panicle was found in BRR1 dhan50 (140) followed by BRR1 dhan63 (133) and the highest unfilled grain was produced by BRR1 dhan81 (50) (Table 3).

Table 3: Mean Grain yield and yield contributing characteristics of the five rice genotypes across ten locations during Boro 2021-22 season.

Genotypes	Locations										Mean
	Rangpur (Sadar)	Rangpur (Mithapukur)	Rajshahi (Paba)	Rajshahi (Godagari)	Sirajganj (Sadar)	Cumilla (Debidar)	Feni (Sadar)	Kushia (Sadar)	Habiganj (Sadar)	BRR1, Gazipur	
Grain Yield (tha⁻¹)											
V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2	7.24	7.09	5.95	6.45	8.03	7.40	5.36	5.88	6.45	5.89	6.57
V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1	7.28	7.16	5.98	6.48	8.37	6.00	5.25	6.72	5.96	5.71	6.49
V3=BRR1 dhan50(Ck)	6.34	6.35	5.76	6.22	7.38	5.43	5.84	6.52	4.73	4.71	5.93
V4=BRR1 dhan63(Ck)	6.91	6.51	5.67	6.05	8.12	5.63	6.18	6.83	4.99	6.26	6.31
V5=BRR1 dhan81(Ck)	6.23	5.50	4.98	5.44	5.86	4.97	6.01	5.78	4.99	5.40	5.52
LSD											0.18
CV (%)	5.84										
Growth duration (Days)											
V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2	154	150	152	150	155	157	144	154	156	152	153
V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1	156	152	155	152	152	155	145	155	158	151	153
V3=BRR1 dhan50(Ck)	158	160	157	154	155	154	153	156	163	155	157
V4=BRR1 dhan63(Ck)	152	149	153	147	149	146	146	156	156	154	151
V5=BRR1 dhan81(Ck)	154	151	152	146	146	144	144	145	150	146	148
LSD	0.97										0.30
CV (%)	0.39										
Plant height (cm)											
V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2	115	121	118	119	115	107	118	119	119	108	116
V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1	118	121	120	126	116	98	121	119	121	107	117
V3=BRR1 dhan50(Ck)	88	93	95	96	96	83	86	88	94	89	91
V4=BRR1 dhan63(Ck)	85	90	91	92	94	81	97	89	91	84	89
V5=BRR1 dhan81(Ck)	101	101	105	98	102	80	106	101	97	95	99
LSD	4.58										1.44
CV (%)	2.77										
Thousand grain weight(g)											
V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2	23.67	24.27	23.38	24.32	24.53	24.33	21.73	24.32	22.63	23.00	23.6
V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1	23.27	23.57	21.98	22.02	23.72	23.44	21.12	23.28	23.41	22.93	22.8
V3=BRR1 dhan50(Ck)	19.03	18.97	17.17	18.62	19.60	18.00	19.20	19.03	17.54	17.59	18.4
V4=BRR1 dhan63(Ck)	22.10	22.20	21.48	20.41	20.87	20.63	21.60	22.08	20.53	20.58	21.2
V5=BRR1 dhan81(Ck)	21.97	22.17	20.15	20.55	20.53	22.23	21.97	22.18	20.99	21.49	21.4
LSD	0.92										0.29
CV (%)	2.64										
Panicles/m²(no)											
V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2	273	243	238	235	285	274	248	266	257	255	257
V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1	275	268	248	260	282	263	251	257	243	231	258
V3=BRR1 dhan50(Ck)	270	279	267	274	276	247	279	281	246	297	272

V4=BRRRI dhan63(Ck)	281	261	246	284	306	253	251	291	241	276	269
V5=BRRRI dhan81(Ck)	272	240	237	245	228	228	261	273	234	259	248
LSD	13.29										4.20
CV (%)	3.15										
Grains/Panicle(no)											
V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2	125	129	123	127	133	124	118	115	126	119	124
V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1	134	141	118	122	144	125	118	138	130	134	130
V3=BRRRI dhan50(Ck)	159	135	139	137	146	134	132	151	133	130	140
V4=BRRRI dhan63(Ck)	137	136	123	130	141	133	126	142	111	150	133
V5=BRRRI dhan81(Ck)	145	132	115	118	137	126	122	131	121	125	127
LSD	7.57										2.39
CV (%)	3.57										
Unfilled grains/Panicle(no)											
V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2	33	51	26	34	35	37	42	46	43	46	39
V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1	60	62	59	39	24	34	43	31	47	51	45
V3=BRRRI dhan50(Ck)	35	48	49	46	32	38	46	25	47	51	42
V4=BRRRI dhan63(Ck)	43	46	51	52	35	51	34	37	53	48	45
V5=BRRRI dhan81(Ck)	52	59	64	47	47	62	43	34	49	47	50
LSD	8.84										2.7
CV (%)	12.32										

Additive main effects and multiplicative interaction1 biplot for GY

As shown in Figure 1, the AMMI 1 biplot shows the relationship between the ordinate and abscissa of the biplot, which represents the primary effects of the first principle component (PCA1) analysis and grain yield (GY). This biplot gives insights into genotype-environment interactions (GEI) through the characteristic of GY by plotting the PCA1 scores for both genotypes and environments in relation to GY. The five genotypes tested across ten environments facilitated the understanding of GEI patterns in GY. Based on the GEI analysis, both similarities and differences among the four genotypes were identified. The PCA1 scores for GY accounted for 55.1% of the total variation in GY. The influence of each genotype and environment is better shown by the AMMI 1 biplot pattern. Strong interactions between the genotypes and their environments are indicated by the biplot, which displays all genotypes positioned far from the origin. Environments or genotypes oriented parallel to the ordinate produced yield outputs that were comparable in terms of performance. In addition, yields were higher on the right side of the axis center than on the left. In this study, the Figure 4 showed genotype V4, V2 and V1 located to the right of the center, performed better than V3 and V5 in terms of GY.

Figure 1: Additive main effects and multiplicative interaction1 (AMMI1) biplots based on PC1 illustrating G×E interactions of the 4 rice genotypes across ten sites for GY. E₁=Sadar, Rangpur, E₂= Mithapukur, Rangpur, E₃= Paba, Rajshahi, E₄= Godagari, Rajshahi, E₅= Sadar, Sirajganj, E₆= Debidwar, Cumilla, E₇=Sadar, Feni, E₈=Sadar, Kushtia, E₉= Sadar, Habiganj, E₁₀=BRRRI H/Q, Gazipur. V₁=BR9930-2-3-2-2, V₂=BR9930-2-3-3-1, V₃= BRRRI dhan50 (ck), V₄= BRRRI dhan63 (ck) and V₅= BRRRI dhan81(ck).

Additive main effects and multiplicative interaction2 biplot

Figure 2 displays the biplot for the Additive Main Effects and Multiplicative Interaction Model 2 (AMMI 2) for premium quality rice genotypes. Unlike Figure 1, where PCA1 was tested against agronomic variables, this biplot plots the first principal component (PCA1) scores for both environments and genotypes against the second principal component (PCA2) scores. The biplot was created using the PCA1 and PCA2 scores of both environments and genotypes. The AMMI 2 analysis demonstrated the value of PCA2 scores in addition to PCA1 in describing the complexity of genotype-environment interactions (GEI) in various contexts and determining the adaptability of the genotypes. In this study, PCA2 contributed 28.2% to the variation for grain yield (GY). Additionally, it was found that the first two PCA components accounted for 83.2% of the G + G × E interaction variation across the six agronomic traits incorporated in the AMMI 2 biplot. For GY, all genotypes were situated far from the origin, indicating substantial interaction. Locations E1, E2, E3 and E4 showed minimal contribution to PCA1, while locations E5, E6, E7, E8 and E9 had high scores for both PCA1 and PCA2 in terms of grain yield performance. Genotypes V1, V2 and V5 had substantial interactions with the E6, E5 regions and E7 region. Otherhand genotype V3 and v4 had greater interaction with E8region.

Figure 2: Additive main effects and multiplicative interaction2 (AMMI2) biplots

based on PC1 and PC2 illustrating G×E interactions of the 5 rice genotypes across ten sites for GY.

E₁=Sadar, Rangpur, E₂= Mithapukur, Rangpur, E₃= Paba, Rajshahi, E₄= Godagari, Rajshahi, E₅= Sadar, Sirajganj, E₆= Debidwar, Cumilla, E₇=Sadar, Feni, E₈=Sadar, Kushtia, E₉= Sadar, Habiganj, E₁₀=BRRI H/Q, Gazipur.V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2, V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1, V3= BRRI dhan50 (ck), V4= BRRI dhan63 (ck)andV4= BRRI dhan81(ck).

GGE biplot

The GGE biplot shown in Figure 3 illustrates the genotype-environment interaction (GEI) for grain yield (GY). Principal component 1 (PC1) accounted for 71.04% of the total variation, while principal component 2 (PC2) explained an additional 17.87%, giving a combined contribution of 88.91% to the overall variation in GY traits. The GGE biplot provides valuable insights into GEI effects, enabling the identification of genotypes that are best suited to specific environments, as no genotype consistently excels in all settings.

Figure 3: GGE biplots based on PC1 and PC2 showing G×E interactions of the five rice genotypes across ten locations for GY.E₁=Sadar, Rangpur, E₂= Mithapukur, Rangpur, E₃= Paba, Rajshahi, E₄= Godagari, Rajshahi, E₅= Sadar,

Sirajganj, E₆= Debidwar, Cumilla, E₇=Sadar, Feni, E₈=Sadar, Kushtia, E₉= Sadar, Habiganj, E₁₀=BRRI H/Q, Gazipur. V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2, V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1, V3= BRRI dhan50 (ck), V4= BRRI dhan63 (ck) and V5= BRRI dhan81(ck).

Differences in performance were reflected in the environment vectors for the eight agronomic traits. Specifically, locations E5, E6, and E9 displayed the longest vectors, indicating their strong impact on genotype performance. Genotypes aligned with the direction of these locations generally yielded higher. It appeared that V2 positioned in the highest locations among the genotypes. While those behind the origin, such as V5, did not cluster with the environments and performed less favorably.

Which-won-where

The GGE biplot for the "which-won-where" pattern, presented in Figure 4, indicates that the first and second principal components (PCA1 and PCA2) together explained 88.91% of the total variation in grain yield (GY). The test environments were grouped into five sectors, each representing a distinct mega-environment.

Figure 4: Polygon views of GGE biplot for which-won-where analysis of the five rice genotypes under the effects of genotypes-by environment interactions for GY. E₁=Sadar, Rangpur, E₂= Mithapukur, Rangpur, E₃= Paba, Rajshahi, E₄= Godagari, Rajshahi, E₅=

Sadar, Sirajganj, E₆= Debidwar, Cumilla, E₇=Sadar, Feni, E₈=Sadar, Kushtia, E₉= Sadar, Habiganj, E₁₀=BRRI H/Q, Gazipur. V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2, V2=BR9930-2-3-3-1, V3= BRRI dhan50 (ck), V4= BRRI dhan63 (ck) and V5= BRRI dhan81(ck).

The vertex genotypes in these sectors were identified as the top performers for their respective mega-environments, while genotypes that did not fall within any sector demonstrated weaker interaction with the environments. In this study, V1 emerged as the best-performing genotypes within the largest mega-environment consisting with 5 locations. V2 performed best in 3 locations. V5 had poor relation with the environments.

Mean vs. stability

The mean performance vs the stability of the genotypes that were examined is shown in Figure 5. Based on singular value partitioning (SVP=2), the average environment coordinate (AEC) is represented by two lines: one for the ordinate and one for the abscissa, both of which meet at the biplot's origin.

Figure 5: Mean vs. stability based on PC1 and PC2 showing G × E interactions of the five rice genotypes across ten locations for GY. E₁=Sadar, Rangpur, E₂= Mithapukur, Rangpur, E₃= Paba, Rajshahi, E₄= Godagari, Rajshahi, E₅= Sadar, Sirajganj, E₆= Debidwar, Cumilla, E₇=Sadar, Feni, E₈=Sadar, Kushtia, E₉= Sadar, Habiganj, E₁₀=BRRI H/Q, Gazipur. V1=BR9930-2-3-2-2, V2=BR9930-

2-3-3-1, V3= BRRI dhan50 (ck), V4= BRRI dhan63 (ck) and V4= BRRI dhan81(ck).

The abscissa of the AEC, indicated by a single arrow, reflects the main effect of the ideal genotype, while the ordinate, marked with dotted lines outside the biplot, demonstrates the genotypic-environment interaction (GEI) effect and lower stability. This division by the ordinate separates genotypes that performed above average from those with below-average yields. In this analysis, the genotype ranking followed the pattern $V1 > V2 > V4$ Average $> V3 > V5$. The stability of each genotype is determined by its projection onto the AEC ordinate; genotypes with minimal projection are considered the most stable, whereas those with longer projections exhibit instability. In this case, V2 displayed greater stability with above mean performance.

Discriminativeness vs. representativeness

Figure 6: Discriminativeness and representativeness GGE biplot of the five premium quality rice genotypes across ten locations for GY. E_1 =Sadar, Rangpur, E_2 = Mithapukur, Rangpur, E_3 = Paba, Rajshahi, E_4 = Godagari, Rajshahi, E_5 = Sadar, Sirajganj, E_6 = Debidwar, Cumilla, E_7 =Sadar, Feni, E_8 =Sadar, Kushtia, E_9 = Sadar, Habiganj, E_{10} =BRRH H/Q, Gazipur. V_1 =BR9930-2-3-2-2, V_2 =BR9930-2-3-3-1, V_3 = BRRI dhan50 (ck), V_4 = BRRI dhan63 (ck) and V_5 = BRRI dhan81(ck).

Figure 6 of the GGE biplot study illustrates the "discriminativeness vs. representativeness" of the genotypes. The vector length for each environment revealed the discriminatory ability of the environment, while the angle formed by each vector with the abscissa denotes representativeness. In the present study, E5 showed the longest vector. The angle of E2 was the very close to AEC and the largest angle observed for E8.

DISCUSSION

Two advanced breeding lines having premium quality properties with three check varieties were planted across ten locations in Bangladesh using RCBD design. Similar type of research also seen in et al., 2017; Biswash et al., 2023; Dewan et al., 2017; Karmakar et al., 2020). To evaluate the genotypes performance, stability, and genotype-environment interaction (GEI) impacts, the analysis uses reliable statistical models such as AMMI and GGE biplots. Similar models were also used by (Rahmati et al., 2024; Daemo et al., 2023; Habtegebriel, 2022; Yan & Tinker, 2006) to determine the superior genotypes in METs. In this study all the traits showed significant variation, indicates that these traits are influenced by both genetic and environmental factors. Esan et al. (2023) also found the same result. Taleghani et al. (2023) revealed that the environment had a significant effect on all features at the 1% probability level, revealing a difference among the experimental environment. These interactions involve the careful selection of genotypes that are either adapted to specific environments or stable across multiple contexts. According to Habtegebriel (2022), researchers in a breeding program place a high priority on well-adapted and consistent yield in a variety of habitats to reduce the danger of yield loss due to climatic conditions. Among the five tested genotypes, BR9930-2-3-2-2 (V_1) genotype produced highest mean grain yield (6.57 t ha^{-1}) across the environment, another advanced line BR9930-2-3-3-1 (V_2) following closely (6.49 tons per hectare). That indicates newer advanced lines like V_1 and V_2 can replace older varieties in terms of yield. Both the advanced line showed greater plant height, which is desirable in some agricultural systems for ease of harvest and even trigger the yield production

(Zhao et al., 2020). Growth duration was lowest for BRRI dhan81 variety (V5) followed by V4, V1 and V2. Vergara et al. (1966) told that a short-duration crop would offer various advantages over a long-duration crop, even if total grain yields were similar. V4 performed well in terms of thousand grain weight and panicles per meter square and, exhibiting the lowest weight (18.48 grams) and highest number of panicles per meter square (272), which suggests that this genotype might be favored for its grain quality. Many researchers found that fine grain quality could lead to better market acceptance due to improved milling and eating quality (Ghasemzadeh et al., 2018; Sharma & KHANNA, 2020; Sultana et al., 2022).

Both AMMI and GGE biplots provide insights into the stability and adaptability of the genotypes across different environments (Dewan et al., 2017; Esan et al., 2023; Yan & Tinker, 2006). In the present study, the AMMI analysis revealed that the environment (E) accounted for the majority (58.21%) of the total variation in grain yield, followed by GEI (27.33%). This suggests that environmental factors play the most significant role in determining rice yield, but genotype selection based on stability and adaptability can mitigate these environmental effects. From the GGE biplots, it was evident that V1 was the highest-performing genotype across most environments, where V2 also performing well with higher stability. The analysis of the "which-won-where" GGE biplot showed that V1 was the top performer in most environments, making it suitable for widespread cultivation. On the other hand, V2 excelled in a few specific environments, indicating its potential as a location-specific variety.

The advanced breeding lines tested in this study show significant promise, especially V1 and V2 for introduction into environments where premium quality properties are key breeding goals. Although plant breeders at BRRI prioritize enhancing grain yield to address the increasing population and shrinking cultivable land. But these genotypes showed yield potential and offer others benefits, particularly quality grains, which can contribute to earn foreign currencies through

exporting and ultimately can contribute to countries GDP.

CONCLUSION

The use of complex statistical models like as AMMI and GGE biplots enables a deeper understanding of genotype performance and stability in multi-environmental trials, which is necessary for the effective development of rice varieties. This study successfully identifies BR9930-2-3-2-2 (V1) as the high-yielding genotype, BR9930-2-3-3-1 (V2) is the most stable and well adaptable to multiple environments. These advanced lines demonstrated strong potential in all environments and should be considered for further trial across different agroecological regions for possible release.

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